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Effects of Scaffolding Instructional Strategy on Performance and Attitude in Biology among Secondary School Students in Ekiti State, Nigeria

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Abstract:

The study examined the effects of scaffolding instructional strategy on students' Performance and Attitude in Biology among secondary school students in Ekiti State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study ascertained the difference in the pre-test and post-test mean scores of students exposed to scaffolding instructional strategy and conventional method of teaching Biology in secondary schools. The study investigated the difference in the performance and attitudinal mean scores of students in experimental and control groups. This study adopted a two group quasi-experimental of pre-test, post-test and control group design. The population for the study comprised 12,585 SSSII students in 205 public secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The sample for the study consisted of 159 SSS II students in the selected schools using multistage sampling procedure. Two instruments were used to collect data, Biology Performance Test (BPT) and Students' Attitudinal Scale (SAS). The face and content validity of the instruments were ensured by experts. The reliability of the instrument (BPT) was established using test-retest method of testing reliability while that of SAS was established through Cronbach's Alpha reliability testing. The reliability coefficients of 0.81 and 0.87 were obtained for BPT and SAS respectively. Two research questions were raised and answered while four hypotheses were generated and tested. The data collected were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation. Hypotheses 1-4 were tested using t-test. The findings of the study showed that: there was significant effect of scaffolding instructional strategy on the performance mean scores, attitudinal mean scores, of students in Biology after treatment. Based on the findings it was recommended that, implementing scaffolding as instructional strategy can significantly enhance students' academic performance and Attitude in Biology, Therefore, the use of scaffolding instructional strategy should be included into Biology curriculum.

Key Words: Scaffolding, Performance, Attitude

1. Introduction

Biology is a Science subject concerned with the study of living organisms, It allows man to understand the variety of life forms, conservation and viable use of natural resources. Biology as a Science subject occupies a central position in the Science curriculum its inclusion as a core subject for Science students cannot be de-emphasized.

Biology serves as a prerequisite subject for most Science and related professions like Biochemistry, Pharmacy, Medicine, Nursing and Environmental Sciences among others. According to Umoru and Onoja, (2017), the basic knowledge and skills acquired from the subject can be of tremendous help to man and the society. The impact of Biology on the life of living organisms is wide; all ensuring that the required standard of living for both plants and animals are maintained (Ugwadu & Joda, 2015).

Biology is practical oriented subject which focuses more on knowledge application than mere knowledge acquisition, its objectives as contained in the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2014)

includes among others are; to equip learners with meaningful and relevant knowledge of Biology, adequate laboratory and field skills, this can be achieved through effective teaching strategies. It is observed that the performance of students in external examination are not encouraging, However, Umaru, (2011), Joda & Mohammed, (2017) and Joda, (2018) in their reports showed that there is a persistent low performance in Senior Secondary Certificate Examination and National Examination Council Biology examinations annually. This low performance in Biology could be attributed to poor instructional delivery approaches adopted by teachers, students' attitudinal problems, teachers' laxity towards teaching, concentration on few topics for examination purpose and students inability to recall previously learnt materials (Umoru & Onoja, 2017).

The West African Examination Council (WAEC) chief Examiner's Report (2018) pointed out that among the factors that cause low achievement of students in Biology; poor instructional delivery approach to teaching by teachers is the most prominent factor. It is observed that most Biology teachers seem not to understand other teaching strategies but hold on to the old chalk and talk method. Similarly, given students tasks seems not in vogue, few teachers that ventured into giving tasks do not mark to correct the students appropriately.

The low achievement of students in Biology at Senior Secondary Certificate Examination raises doubt about the effectiveness of current teaching approaches in use by Biology teachers. More so some topics are perceived as difficult topics by secondary school Biology students. Exposing learners to the understanding of basic concepts in Biology and achieving desirable outcomes requires the use of creative, innovative and interactive teaching approaches such as scaffolding teaching strategies which may arouse the interest of the learners, demystify difficult concepts in Biology improve their attitude and performance. In addition, it is counter-productive to present ideas to learners without fully engaging them in the learning process. According to Olagunju and Akpan (2019) practical skills should be considered when taking topics in biology as it has an effect on students' skills.

Looking at the past records of Biology from West African Senior Certificate Examination from the year 2017 to 2022 indicated that there is fluctuation in the results. The number of students with grade A1 – B3 in each of the year is observed to be dwindling also the number of students with the overall grades are not encouraging compared with the total population that wrote the examination. Also the number of students that have C4 –C6 are many which indicate that larger percentage of the students have credit passes which seems not to be adequate as they are likely to record low mark during admission process into higher institution. The number of students that have D7 –E8 and F9 seems to be larger as those in this category may not be admitted into higher institution. Generally the results is fluctuating and not encouraging. This fluctuation in the performance of students in Biology has become an issue of great concern in recent times, however this might be as a result of teachers teaching strategies, students' attitude towards Biology, lack of adequate instructional materials among others.

Table 1: Analysis of Results of West African School Certificate Examination from 2017-2022

<i>Year</i>	<i>Total Candidate</i>	<i>A1-B3</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>C4-C6</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>D7-E8</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>F9</i>	<i>%</i>
2017	5641	1120	20	3333	59	570	10	618	11
2018	5578	1248	22.4	3389	61	466	8	475	9
2019	5563	824	15	3098	56	1069	19	572	10
2020	7161	642	9	3007	42	1719	24	1790	25
2021	6707	4765	71	1286	19	133	2	523	8
2022	7252	4230	58	1800	25	560	8	622	9

Source: Ekiti State Ministry of Education, Planning, Research and Statistics Department (2023)

It is observed that the fluctuation performance in the result released by West African Examination Council could be improve if new teaching methods are adopted by Secondary School Biology teacher because exposing learners to the understanding of basic concepts in Biology and achieving desirable outcomes requires the use of creative, innovative and interactive teaching strategy such as scaffolding instructional strategy.

The word scaffolding is derived from construction work, where it represents a temporary structure that is used to erect a building. In education, scaffolding strategy is a strategy of teaching where the teacher gives support or assistance to students in a learning situation which is tailored to the needs of the students with the aim of assisting the students to achieve their learning goals. The teacher assigns the new tasks to students in stages and also allows the students to generate tasks and complete the tasks individually. Scaffolding instructional strategy may assist the students while learning new concept or skill in Biology this could eventually foster ability to use the knowledge acquired independently by the learners.

Scaffolding Instructional strategy may provide sufficient support to promote learning when concepts and skills are being first introduced to students. The teachers help the students master a task or a concept by providing support. These supports may include models, hints, partial solutions, think-aloud modelling, questioning, resource, compelling task, templates, coaching, guides and guidance, among others. These supports are gradually removed as students develop autonomous learning strategies, thus promoting their own cognitive, affective and psychomotor learning skills and knowledge.

Scaffolding is a teaching strategy which may provide creative ideas to individual learners and makes each interact with peers and transfer scientific knowledge. Transfer of knowledge here means knowledge gained while solving a particular problem in Biology is used to solve a likened task or used in another topic. The strategy limits the idea of teacher-centred instructional strategy where the transfer of teachers' knowledge to students in the order. It encourages the individual learner to be more industrious and be self-confident. The activities are student centred, and students are encouraged to ask their own questions, carry out their own finding and draw their own conclusion. Brunner,(1977) stated that scaffolding involves helpful structured interaction between an adult and a child with the aim of helping the child achieve a specific goal, the purpose of the support is to allow the child to achieve higher levels of development by simplifying the task or idea, motivating the child.

Scaffolding instructional strategy is designed for students to be actively engaged 'in doing things' rather than in 'learning about' something. In doing things, the learner will not be passive; he will be a party to the provision of solution to the problem. The learner is not only learning about what others brought as ideas, but he also brings the solution to the problem as a result of his observation, critical thinking and manipulations

Scaffolding instruction as an instructional strategy originated from Lev Vygotsky's social-cultural theory and his concept of the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD). The Zone of Proximal Development is the distance between what children can do by themselves and the next learning that they can be helped to achieve with competent assistance (Margaret, 2018). It is the zone where instruction and learning can take place. The activities provided in scaffolding instruction are just beyond the level of what the learner can do alone. Scaffolding instruction is temporary, as the learners' abilities increase the scaffolding provided by the more knowledgeable other is progressively withdrawn. The learner may be able to complete the task or master the concepts independently. Therefore, the goal of the educator when using the scaffolding instructional strategy is for the student to become an independent, self-regulating learner and problem solver.

According to Janneke, Monique and Jos (2010) scaffolding is the support given by a teacher to a student when performing a task that the student might otherwise not be able to accomplish. There are three essential features of scaffolding that facilitate learning. The first feature has to do with the interaction between the expert (teacher) and the learner. This interaction should be collaborative for it to be effective. In the second feature learning should take place in the learner's Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD). This is the zone where instruction and learning can take place. To achieve that, the expert needs to be aware of the learner's current level of knowledge and then work to a certain extent beyond that level. The third feature of scaffolding is that the scaffold, the support and guidance provided by the expert, is gradually removed as the learner becomes more skillful.

The support and guidance provided to the learner are compared to the scaffolds in building construction where the scaffolds provide both "adjustable and temporal" support to the building under construction. The support and guidance provided to learners facilitate internalization of the knowledge needed to complete the task. This support is weaned gradually until the learner is independent. The scaffolding learning approaches become most effective when it contributes to the learning environment. Scaffolding is applied gradually, modified and finally removed according to the needs of the student.

Scaffolding strategy is a student-centred strategy which gives students more ownership of their learning, while gradually decreasing the teacher's role in the process. It also allows students to grasp the content in small chunks without being overwhelmed. Students receive guidance at the beginning of a task. Teacher support slowly decreases as students start to demonstrate mastery. Each stage allows the students to build upon the previous stage, and the teacher becomes more of a facilitator while the students become independent. Scaffolding strategy focuses on raising students' abilities one step at a time and removing support as they progress. This encourages and enables the students to be active learners in the teaching and learning process. Scaffolding begins with materials that are just a step beyond what the learners are able to accomplish unassisted. The teacher builds on the students' previous knowledge and then removes the support, allowing the learners to master the content.

In spite of the possible influences of scaffolding instructional strategy on students' attitude and performance in Biology, there are possibilities that other factors can also affect students' attitude and performance in Biology. For instance, findings from the study of Popoola (2014) showed that teacher's characteristics, students' attitude, gender differences, school location are among the factors that influence students' performance and attitude.

Students' performances play a crucial role in educational system. Yusuf, Onifade and Bello, (2016) refers academic performance as a measurable and observable behaviors of a student within a specific period. In schools, student's successes are reflected in their academic performances. The academic performance is considered as a criterion to judge their total potentiality and capacities. Therefore, academic performance occupies a very important place in education and learning as well. Morgan (2010) defined academic performance as an assessment strategy by which the evidence about students' learning is gathered through students' work on a performed task. That is achievement is reflected by the extent to which skills and knowledge has been impacted to a learner.

It is observed that the performance of students in Biology is influenced by the instructional strategy adopted by teachers in secondary schools, in order to get a desirable outcome. Biology as science is supposed to be taught using effective teaching strategy, giving credence to the above Ahmed and Abimbola (2011) opined that poor teaching method adopted by teachers at the senior secondary school level in Nigeria have been identified as one of the major factor contributing to poor performance of students in Biology. Biology as a science subject focuses more on knowledge application than mere knowledge acquisition therefore it should be taught using effective instructional strategy in order to enhanced better performance.

Attitude is defined as positive or negative emotions or feelings that a person feels towards the socially significant object or a person. Attitude towards Biology seems to plays a crucial role in the teaching and learning of Biology. It can affect students' performance in the subject. Attitudes are developed by following the example or opinion of others (teacher, parent or friend). It can also be the product of imitation from the teaching-learning situation. As a result, the learner draws from the teacher's disposition to develop attitude, which tends to affects students' performance towards Biology.

Kolawole and Popoola (2011) stated that negative attitudes are developed by students when they experience frequent and repeated failures or problems when carrying out mathematical tasks and these negative attitudes may become relatively permanent. These authors further stressed that, when children first go to school, they do not have a negative attitude towards any subject but a positive attitude. However, as they progress, their attitudes become negative at senior secondary school. The authors further found significant differences between younger and older students' attitude towards Biology with the senior classes having lower attitudes than the junior classes.

Attitude plays an important role towards the future of Science students. Students' attitude towards Science affects their academic performance in Science. Identifying as well as influencing their attitudes is significant in educational research studies. Attitude could be positive, negative or neutral. Any concept that specifies an individual's feeling of likeness or dislike to anything is termed his/her attitude towards that item. Attitude can be a method, disposition, feeling or condition in respect of an individual or object, particularly of the mind. According to Nasr and Soltani, (2011), attitudes are like academic achievement because they are significant factors in ensuring students success. It is important for Science teachers to ensure that students have positive attitudes in Science subjects, but studies shows that the way students are

taught in Science classrooms seems not to be interesting to them. Student's success in Science is affected by their attitudes.

Conventional teaching method or traditional teaching method involving instructors and students interacting in a face to face manner in the classroom. It is a method aimed at enabling the teacher to communicate information to the learner, the common mode in this communication is the spoken word while the learners are the passive recipients. Many teachers are still teaching their students in the same manner as how they were taught and how their own teachers were taught, not much of progress in terms of the teaching perspectives (Anglin & Anglink, 2018). Transformation to these conventional methods of teaching results in fear and reluctance from teachers who find the change hard and risky.

Devinders and Zaitun (2016) cited that many teachers are still using conventional teaching classrooms while the teacher is explaining and writing on the board, students would be copying the same thing into their notes, some day-dreaming and some sleeping. Conventional teaching is also limiting room for more creative thinking and also not considering individual differences.

The study investigated effects of scaffolding instructional strategy on students' Learning outcomes in Biology among senior secondary school students in Ekiti state, Nigeria.

2. Statement of the Problem

Biology is a practical subject that requires to be taught in a manner that the students will be actively engaged in the teaching and learning processes. It was observed that most Biology teachers in Secondary schools seems not to teach the subject by involving students in practical activities unless after they might have received instruction to practical from the examining body towards preparation for external examination. In spite of the importance placed on Biology in Science education, The report from West African Examination Council (WAEC) 2017-2022 Senior Secondary School Examination (SSCE) showed that students performance in Biology examinations in Ekiti State appear to be fluctuating.

This fluctuating performance could be attributed to the problem of teaching strategy adopted by most Biology teachers. The researcher personal experience as a biology teacher showed that most biology teachers are used to conventional method of teaching which is teachers centered, students depend on memorization without having a complete understanding of the subject. It is also observed that Biology teacher seem not to encourage interaction and sharing of ideas among students. This perhaps serve as impediment for Biology to fully achieve its objectives.

Observations also showed that poor teaching methods adopted by teachers at Senior Secondary Schools have been identified as one of the major factors contributing to dwindling in the performance of students over the years. It is also observed that teachers do not give tasks to the students, the persistent use of this method make students passive rather than active listners this may not promote insightful learning and long term retention of some abstract Biological concepts.

Researcher also observed that Biology students depend on memorization of fact without understanding the basic concepts furthermore, it appears students attitude is being influenced by the teachers disposition and teaching methods which may consequently have effect on their performance. Therefore, this study investigated the effects of scaffolding instructional strategy on secondary school students' learning outcomes in Biology in Ekiti state, Nigeria.

3. Purpose of the Study

This study investigated effects of scaffolding instructional strategy on senior secondary school students' Performance and Attitude in Biology in Ekiti State, Nigeria. This study specifically:

- i. examined the difference in the performance and attitudinal mean scores of students in the experimental and control groups before treatment in Biology;
- ii. investigated the effects of scaffolding instructional strategy and conventional method on students' learning outcomes in Biology;

4. Research Questions

The following research questions were raised for the study:

1. What is the performance of students before and after treatments in Biology?
2. What is the attitude of students towards Biology before and after treatments?

5. Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated for this study and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the performance mean scores of students in the experimental and control groups before treatment in Biology.
2. There is no significant difference in the attitudinal mean scores of students in the experimental and control groups before treatment in Biology.
3. There is no significant effect of scaffolding and conventional methods on performance mean scores of students in Biology after treatment.
4. There is no significant effect of scaffolding and conventional methods on attitudinal mean scores of students Biology after treatment

6. Research Design

The research design for the study was pre-test, post-test control group quasi-experimental research design (one experimental and one control group). The design investigated the effects of the independent variables on the dependent variables. The pre-tests was conducted to establish performance and attitude of students in both experimental and the control groups prior to the treatment. This equally ascertained the homogeneity between the two groups. Post-tests was administered after the treatments in order to measure possible improvement on students' academic performance and change in attitude in all the groups.

7. Population

The population for the study consisted of 12,585 Senior Secondary School Two (SSS II) students of Biology from 210 public secondary schools in the 16 Local Government Areas (LGAs) of Ekiti State as at the time of the study (Ministry of Education, Ekiti State, 2022).

Sample and Sampling Techniques

The sample for the study consisted of 159 SSS II students who were selected using multistage sampling procedure. The first stage involved the selection of One Local Government Area using simple random sampling technique. In stage two, four public secondary schools were selected from the Local Government Area through stratified random sampling technique using location (rural and urban) as the basis of stratification. This implied that, two schools were selected from urban and two schools from rural. In stage three, SSS II intact class of each of the four schools was used for the study.

8. Instruments

The Study made use of two instruments namely Biology Performance Test (BPT), and Student Attitudinal Scales (SAS)

Data Analysis

The data collected were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The research questions were answered using mean, standard deviation and bar chart. The hypotheses were tested using inferential statistics. Specifically, hypotheses 1 - 4 were tested using t-test, All the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

9. Results

Question 1: What is the performance of students before and after treatments in Biology?

In order to answer the question, the aggregate scores of students' performance in Biology test before and after the treatment were obtained for each of the groups and computed with the descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation.

The result is presented in table 2.

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation Showing Students' Performance in Biology before and after Treatment

Group	N	Before Treatment		After Treatment		Mean Difference
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Experimental	86	21.7	9.93	57.2	10.21	35.5
Control	73	19.5	9.25	26.8	6.16	7.2
Grand Mean	159	20.7		43.2		22.5

Table 2 shows that before the treatment, the mean scores of students' performance in the experimental group was 21.7 while the mean scores of the control group was 19.5. The grand mean total of both groups was 20.7, suggesting that the knowledge of Biology concept in both groups were homogenous prior to the treatment. However, upon their exposure to the treatment, the grand mean total of both groups increased to 43.2 while the students taught with scaffolding had greater mean scores of 57.2 compare with the mean scores of students taught conventional methods which was 26.8. With the highest mean difference of 35.5, it could be adjudged that scaffolding had the greater potential impact on enhancing student's performance in Biology than the conventional method with mean difference value of 7.2. This further depicted in Figure iii

Fig iii: Students' Performance in Biology before and after Treatment

Question 2: What is the attitude of students towards Biology before and after treatments?

In order to answer the question, the aggregate scores of Students Attitudinal Scale in Biology before and after the treatment were obtained for each of the groups and computed with the descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation. The result is presented in table 3

Table 3: Students' Attitude towards Biology before and after Treatment

Group	N	Before Treatment		After Treatment		Mean Difference
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Experimental	86	45.65	6.568	56.36	6.629	10.7
Control	73	47.25	8.572	53.72	9.299	6.5
Grand Mean	159	46.4		55.1		8.8

Table 3 shows that the experimental group had a mean attitude score of 45.65 before treatment and 56.36 after treatment, with a 10.7 mean difference while the control group had a mean attitude score of 47.25 before treatment and 53.72 after treatment, with a 6.5 difference. The results indicate that both the experimental and control groups experienced an increase in their mean attitude scores after treatment.

However, the experimental group had a larger mean difference compared to the control group, suggesting that the treatment had a stronger impact on their attitude. This implied that the use of scaffolding change students attitude towards Biology than the conventional method. The result is further depicted in figure iv:

Fig. iv: Students' Attitude towards Biology before and after treatment
Testing of Hypotheses

Hypotheses 1: There is no significant difference in the performance mean scores of students in the experimental and control groups before treatment in Biology.

Table 4: t-test showing Differences in Students' Performance in Biology between the Experimental and Control groups before Treatment

Group	N	Mean	S. D	df	t	p-value
Experimental	86	21.67	9.925	157	1.387	0.168
Control	73	19.54	9.252			

$P > 0.05$

Table 4 shows that t-test was conducted to compare the performance mean scores of students in Biology for experimental and control groups. The result indicated that there was no significant difference in performance mean scores of students for experimental ($M = 21.67$, $SD = 9.93$) and control ($M = 19.54$, $SD = 9.25$; $t(157) = 1.387$, $p = .168$). Therefore, the null hypothesis was not rejected because the p-value of 0.168 was greater than 0.05 level of significance. In another word, there was no significant difference in the performance mean scores of students in the experimental and control groups before treatment in Biology. Hence the two groups that is experimental and control groups were homogenous.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the attitudinal mean scores of students in the experimental and control groups before treatment in Biology.

Table 5: t-test Showing Differences in Students' Attitude towards Biology between the Experimental and Control Groups before Treatment

Group	N	Mean	S. D	df	t	p-value
Scaffolding	86	45.65	6.568	157	1.331	0.185
Conventional method	73	47.25	8.572			

$P > 0.05$

Table 5 shows that t-test was conducted to compare the attitudinal mean scores of students for experimental and control groups. The result indicate that there was no significant difference in attitudinal

mean scores of students for experimental ($M = 45.65$, $SD = 6.586$) and control ($M = 47.25$, $SD = 8.57$; $t(157) = 1.331$, $p = .185$). Therefore, the null hypothesis was not rejected because the p-value of 0.185 was greater than 0.05 level of significance. In another word, there was no significant difference in the attitudinal mean scores of students in the experimental and control groups before treatment in Biology. This implied that no variation in students attitude toward Biology before the treatment in both experimental and control group.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant effect of scaffolding and conventional methods on performance mean scores of students in Biology after treatment.

Table 6: t-test showing Differences in Students' Performance in Biology between Scaffolding and Conventional Methods after Treatment

Group	N	Mean	S. D	df	t	p-value
Scaffolding	86	57.2	10.21	157	22.264	.000
Conventional method	73	26.8	6.16			

$P < 0.05$

Table 6 shows that t-test was conducted to compare the performance mean scores for experimental and control groups. The result indicated that there was significant difference in performance mean scores for experimental ($M = 57.2$, $SD = 10.21$) and control ($M = 26.8$, $SD = 6.16$; $t(157) = 22.264$, $p = .000$). Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected because the p-value of 0.000 was less than 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, there was significant effect of scaffolding and conventional methods on performance mean scores of students in Biology. This implied that the use of scaffolding instructional strategy enhance students' performance in biology than the conventional method

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant effect of scaffolding and conventional methods on attitudinal mean scores of students in Biology after treatment.

Table 7: t-test Showing Differences in Students' Attitude towards Biology between the Experimental and Control Groups after Treatment

Group	N	Mean	S. D	df	t	p-value
Scaffolding	86	56.36	6.63	15	2.082	.039
Conventional method	73	53.72	9.29	7		

$P < 0.05$

Table 7 shows that t-test was conducted to compare the mean scores of students' attitude towards Biology for experimental and control groups after treatment. The result indicated that there was significant difference in mean scores of students' attitude for experimental ($M = 56.36$, $SD = 6.63$) and control ($M = 53.72$, $SD = 9.29$; $t(157) = 2.082$, $p = .039$). Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected because the p-value of 0.039 was less than 0.05 level of significance. In other word, there was significant effect of scaffolding and conventional methods on attitudinal mean scores of students in Biology after treatment. This implied that the use of scaffolding instructional strategy enhance students attitude towards Biology than the conventional method.

12. Discussion

The study examined effects of scaffolding instructional strategy on secondary school students' learning outcomes in Ekiti State. It was revealed that the performance mean scores of students in pre-test for the experimental and control group were not statistical difference. Hence the two groups were homogenous at the beginning therefore any variation noted was as a result of the treatment.

The findings from this study showed that there was no significant difference in the performance mean scores of students in the experimental and control groups before treatment in Biology. This indicates that there were no significant differences in the baseline knowledge of Biology between the experimental and control groups. Therefore, any changes observed in the post-treatment scores can be attributed to the

treatment itself rather than pre-existing differences in knowledge levels. Also, it was discovered that there was no significant difference in the attitudinal mean scores of students in the experimental and control groups before treatment in Biology which revealed that students attitude at the initial stage towards biology were the same But after the treatment the experimental group had a higher mean attitude compared to the control group, which had a lower mean attitude which implies that scaffolding instructional strategy improved students' attitude towards Biology. This is in line with the finding of Aditi, (2017) who stated that students developed positive attitude towards Science when they were taught using various scaffolding strategies.

Another finding is that there was significant effect of scaffolding and conventional methods on performance mean scores of students in Biology in favour of scaffolding. This revealed that the use of scaffolding in teaching Biology resulted in significantly higher scores compared to the conventional teaching method. Students that were taught using scaffolding seems to have developed higher thinking skills which enable them performed better than their counterparts in the conventional group this is in line with the submission of Clare 2015, which stated that students developed higher thinking skills when scaffolding occurred by an expert (teacher) or peer of higher capability The findings indicate that scaffolding can be an effective approach for improving student performance in Biology. This is in agreement with the finding of Mohammed (2019) which asserted that students taught with scaffolding instructional strategy were more effective than the lecture method of teaching students in Biology. Also, the finding corroborates the findings of Adieze (2016) and Jibrilla (2017), who found out that students taught using scaffolding instructional strategy significantly performed better than the students in the lecture method. .In a classroom interaction it is essential to use learner centred approaches like scaffolding strategy to enhanced effective teaching and learning this will motivate the students to develop interest in the subject. Therefore, incorporating scaffolding techniques into Biology instruction may lead to more comprehensive and meaningful learning outcomes for students.

Furthermore, there was significant effect of scaffolding and conventional methods on attitudinal mean scores of students in Biology after treatment. Students who were taught using scaffolding showed a higher increase in their attitudinal mean scores compared to those who were taught using conventional methods. This revealed that scaffolding is more effective approach in improving students' attitudes towards Biology. This finding aligns with submission of Aditi (2017) that students developed a positive attitude towards Science when they were taught using various scaffolding strategies. Consequently, David (2013) asserted that experience and social interaction play significant roles in learner's cognitive growth using scaffolding techniques as opposed to those that are taught using conventional method. This implies that students who were exposed to scaffolding strategies not only showed improved academic performance in Science but also demonstrated higher levels of engagement and motivation in the subject due to active participation of students during classroom instruction on scaffolding strategy, These findings highlight the importance of incorporating scaffolding techniques in science education to enhance students' attitudes and cognitive development.

13.Conclusion.

Based on the findings of this study, there were homogeneity prior to the beginning of the experiment in the two groups, that is, scaffolding and conventional method. The improvement recorded after the treatment could not have been by chance. It was thus concluded that the use of scaffolding instructional strategy have significant positive effect on the performance and attitude of students in Biology after treatment.

14. Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of this study:

1. Scaffolding instructional strategy should be incorporated into the teaching approach by Biology teachers' in secondary school to enhance students' achievements.
2. Workshops, seminars, training and professional development opportunities should be organized for Biology teachers, to enlighten them on the use of scaffolding approach in teaching Biology.

3. Teachers should focus on creating an inclusive classroom environment that encourages active participation and provides equal opportunities for all students.
4. Curriculum planners should include the use of scaffolding instructional strategy into Biology curriculum.

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